

REVIEW ON LAGHU SUTSHEKAR RAS IN ARDHAVBHEDAK***Dr. Komal Sharma**

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ABSTRACT

Ardhavybhedak is mentioned under shirorog. It is very common disease in present time as well as it is prevailing since past. Ardhavybhedak can be scientifically correlated with migraine due to its cardinal feature of half sided headache. All the three dosha are involved in the manifestation of ardhavybhedak with the predominance of vata or pitta dosha. Management of three dosha can be done by Laghusut Shekhar Ras. Laghusut shekhar Ras is referenced from Rasa Tarangini. Laghu Sutshekhar Ras is prepared from suddha gairika, shunthi and it is processed with nagarbel or betel leaf. It is useful in shirahshool, amlapitta, pittaja unmad disorder etc.

KEYWORDS: Ardhavybhedak, Migraine, Pitta Dosha, Laghu SutShekhar Ras.

INTRODUCTION

Ardhavybhedak is mentioned under shiroroga. According to Acharya Charak,^[1] shiroroga is of five types, Vagabhatta described 10 types and according to Acharya Shushrut^[2], there are 11 types of shiroroga. The most common complaint regarding shiroroga is shirahshool i.e. headache. Different types of shiroroga are vataj, pittaj, kaphaj, sannipataj, raktaj, krimij, kshayaj, suryavart, ardhavybhedak, shankhak and anantvata. Among them ardhavybhedak is found to be most common one often vatika shiroroga. The disease ardhavybhedak is characterized by paroxysmal attacks of headache, which may be unilateral and severe in nature. Ardhavybhedak has all the three dosha with the predominance of vata or vata-kapha. Ardhavybhedak can be correlated with migraine due to its cardinal feature“half sided headache” (Ardha mastak vedana - Chakrapani) and due to its paroxysmal nature.

Etymology of Ardhavbhedak

Ardhavbhedak consists of two words - Ardha and Avabhedak. Ardha denotes half or half side, Ava-poor prognosis and Bheda-breaking through, bursting out and perforating kind of pain. Hence accurate denotation of Ardhavbhedak is bursting or perforating type of pain in unilateral of the head either right or left, Ardhavbhedak means "Ardha mastak vedana" (headache on half part of head), according to Chakrapani.

Pathogenesis of Ardhavbhedak

Due to the different kind of nidana factors vitiate either vata, pitta and kapha or vata and kapha get aggravated, which indulge with rakta in the head, resulting in the manifestation of shirahshoola and invading the half portion of head resulting in ardhavbhedak.

Laghu SutShekhar Ras^[3]

Ingredients of Laghusut Shekhar Ras are

1. Shuddha Swarna Gairika (red ochre)-2 parts
2. Shunthi (zingiber officinale)-1 part
3. Paan (piper betel) - Bhavna Dravya

Chemical Composition

Laghu Sutshekhar Ras contains alkaloids of ginger root and iron oxide. In addition, some alkaloids of betel leaf are also present.

Formulation^[4]

Suwarnagairika-240 gm

Shunthi powder -120 gm

Nagvalli juice extract

All above medicine are collectively taken in one khalwa and grinding is done for 3 days. Then after 3 days vati (tablets) are prepared of 1-4 gunja praman.

Pharmacological Actions

Laghusut Shekhar Ras acts as detoxifier and anti-toxin, which helps to reduce ama in the body and prevent its further formation through its digestive action. This action is contributed by presence of ginger root powder in formulation. Its effects appear on all three dosha, but especially it reduces aggravated pitta. Like Sutshekhar Ras, it also reduces amal and tikshna qualities of pitta dosha.

Ayurvedic Properties and Action of Composition

1. Shuddha Gairika

It is astringent, sweet in taste (Ras), sweet after digestion (vipak), and cool in effect (virya). It is used in treatment of Netra roga, Raktapitta, Hikka, Vata Vikara, Rakta pradar, Kandu, Jwara, Daha, Udar roga.

RAS- Kashaya, Madhur

GUNA- Snigdha, Vishad

VIRYA- Sheeta

VIPAK- Madhur

Action : Pitta Nashak, Vrana ropana, Netrya, Kaphajit

2. Nagvalli / Paan

It is antibacterial, antiseptic, carminative, digestive, expectorant, laxative, stimulant and tonic.

RAS: Kashaya (astringent), Katu (pungent), Tikta (bitter).

GUNA: Laghu (light), Tikshna (sharp), Vishad (non slimy), Sara (mobile, unstable)

VIRYA: Ushna (heating)

VIPAKA: (transformed state after digestion): Katu (pungent)

Action: Shleshmahar (phlegm pacifier), Ruchya (stimulates taste), Vata Hara (pacifies vata)

3. Shunthi

Shunthi acts by its ushna guna, helps in amapachan and agnidipan by its digestive action. It is used in various diseases which originates mainly by agnimandhya and ama like Agnimandhya, shoola, adhman, Atisara, amavata Vibandha, Jwara, Hikka, etc. Aquous extract of ginger was able to protect the gastric mucosa from stress induce mucosal lesions and inhibits gastric acid secretion probably by blocking H⁺ ion, K⁺-ATPase action, inhibiting growth of hpylori and offering anti-oxidant protection against oxidative stress induced gastric damage.

RAS: Katu

GUNA: snigdha

VIRYA: Ushana

VIPAK: Madhur

Action : Deepan, Bhedan, Vata-kaphahar

In short, Laghu sutshekhar Ras acts on^[5]

Dosha -when pitta is aggravated by its Tikshna and Amla guna.

Dushya - Ras, Rakta.

Sthan - Amashay, pakwashay, Raktvaha strotas.

Therapeutic Uses of Laghu Sutshekhar Ras

1. Aam pachak
2. Antiemetic
3. Digestive stimulant
4. Antacid
5. Anti-inflammatory
6. Blood purifier
7. Sinusitis
8. Insomnia
9. Migraine

Matra of Laghu Sutshekhar Ras - 250-500 mg

Anupan - Milk, Sugar

Sevankal - Before or after meal

Probable Mode of Action of Laghu Sutshekhar Ras

• Katu Rasa (40%) and Tikta Rasa (20%) have Deepana–Pachana Karma, which causes Amapachana and thus provides proper metabolism and ultimately balances the Agni. Thus, these Rasa works at Agni dushti stage in the Samprapti of Ardhavabhedaka. Kashaya Rasa (20%) and Ruksha Guna (14.29%) supports the function of these Rasas (Katu – Tikta) due to Shoshana Karma i.e., it helps better absorption at cellular level by enhancing the function of digestion and metabolism. Ushna Virya (66.67%) of Shunthi and Nagavalli has Deepana–Pachana property, which acts as Agnideepaka. It also softens and liquefies the morbid doshas which are ultimately removed due to Virechaka Karma, there by relieving constipation. Snigdha Guna (28.57%), Madhura Vipaka (66.67%) and Madhura Rasa (20%) having the property Srushtavinamutra, which relieves the symptoms of constipation and hyperchlorhydria. Snigdha Guna (28.57%) has Kledana Karma, which acts as a binding agent and strengthens the efficacy of dhatu by providing proper nourishment.

• Laghu Guna (14.29%) and Tikshna Guna (14.29%) have Sroto-shodhaka property, which helps in expelling the morbid doshas. These Guna also have the property of Urdhavabhaga-

doshaharatva, which breaks the Samprapti at Prasaravastha, where Vata alone or Kapha along with Vata causes Urdhavaga pravriti of vitiated doshas. Sheeta Virya (33.33%) of Gairika strengthens the Dhatvagni bala due to its Balya Karma and thus counteracts the Shodhana Karma.

DISCUSSION

Ardhvbhedak being a very common disorder in present scenario. As in this disease, vitiated vata & pitta is primarily responsible factor. Therefore, vata-pitta shamak properties plays an important role in the management of disease. Laghu sutshekhar ras have ingredients, which are mainly pittanashak & vatashamak properties. This medicine balance vata and pita dosha and various disorders that occurs due to vitiation of pitta dosha.

CONCLUSION

Laghu sutshekhar Ras correcting the vitiated state of vata and pitta, improves the Ardhvbhedak. Conceptually it is concluded that the substance having properties like laghu, katu, snigdha, ushana has the effect to decrease the vitiated dravya roop of pitta and maintaining the proper functioning of agni. The herbomineral formulations are simple and effective treatment modality for migraine. The study can prove a real breakthrough in the coming times for treatment of Ardhvbhedak (Migraine).

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